

PROBLEMS OF TEACHING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE AND THEIR MODERN SOLUTIONS

Yusubbayeva N.A.

English teacher, Department of Foreign Philology, Tashkent International University of
Financial Management and Technologies
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14580732>

Abstract. *The teaching of English as a second language (ESL) presents numerous challenges, particularly for learners whose first language differs significantly from English. These challenges include difficulties with pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary acquisition, and cultural nuances. Moreover, issues such as lack of exposure to the language, limited resources, and varying learning speeds can hinder the effectiveness of ESL programs. This paper explores the common issues in ESL education and examines the latest strategies and tools that aim to overcome these challenges, with the goal of improving the overall learning experience for non-native English speakers.*

Keywords: *problems of teaching, English language, education, strategies, grammar.*

Introduction

Teaching English as a Second Language (ESL) has become a crucial part of global education systems, as English is widely recognized as a global lingua franca. However, despite its importance, teaching English to non-native speakers presents numerous challenges. These challenges arise due to the complexity of the English language, which includes its diverse grammar rules, vocabulary, pronunciation, and idiomatic expressions. Furthermore, cultural differences and varying levels of language exposure contribute to the difficulties faced by learners in acquiring English as a second language.

Traditional methods of language instruction, though effective in some contexts, often fall short in addressing the individual needs and learning styles of students. These approaches can also struggle to engage learners in ways that are both meaningful and practical. Consequently, modern solutions in ESL teaching are focusing on innovation through technology, interactive teaching methods, and learner-centered approaches. The integration of digital tools, the use of task-based learning, and incorporating cultural context are among the strategies being employed to overcome these challenges and make language learning more dynamic and effective.

This paper examines the problems faced in ESL education and explores contemporary solutions that have proven effective in enhancing the learning process. Through the adoption of new methodologies and technological advancements, ESL teaching is becoming more adaptive to the diverse needs of learners, providing them with the tools to succeed in acquiring proficiency in English.

Analysis

Problems of Teaching English as a Second Language.

1. Psychological Issues: A common misconception among students is that English is the most difficult subject. This belief, combined with poor results and failures, reinforces this perception. As a result, many students approach the subject with bias and fear, leading to psychological stress, which negatively impacts their performance throughout the year [1]

2. Teaching Methods: The primary goal of teaching English at this stage should focus on developing the student's fundamental language skills, such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing. It is crucial for teachers to have a clear understanding of what they aim to achieve through teaching English. Unfortunately, many educators proceed with their teaching without fully recognizing the difficulties that learners face. Teachers should be aware that students' English proficiency often falls short due to the declining standards of education in schools. Teaching objectives should be practical and aligned with the students' actual proficiency levels. The emphasis should be placed on helping students develop the ability to read and comprehend the language. Currently, there is a tendency to use artificial or indirect methods rather than natural or direct methods for teaching English. In contrast, we learn our native language naturally using the direct method, starting with listening, followed by speaking, reading, and writing — from the simplest to the most complex. However, when learning English as a foreign language, we tend to start with writing, then reading, followed by speaking, and finally listening — an approach that moves from the more difficult skills to the easier ones. This inverted approach significantly increases the likelihood of failure.

One of the reasons for the declining standards of teaching English is the inability of teachers to understand the difference between the teaching of literature and the teaching of language skills. Everybody knows that the study of a language is not an end in itself, it is a means to develop one's power of expression and comprehension can be achieved by mastering stylistic elements of the language. According to A. K. Sharma: “English language teaching in India, you will agree with me, has suffered a lot so much that our students who pass intermediate or degree examinations with English either as a compulsory or as an elective subject can neither speak nor write correct English, may be because the emphasis in our schools and colleges has always been on the conceptual content and the stylistic content has been neglected so far” [2].

3. Problems of Concretizing Abstract Ideas: One significant challenge teachers face is bringing abstract concepts, such as those found in novels, poems, or passages, to life for students. Teachers often struggle to make these abstract ideas tangible, which leads to students having difficulty grasping the content. For example, if a poem about sadness is being taught, the teacher should be able to present it in such a way that students can deeply feel the emotion, even to the point of tears. However, such emotional engagement is rare in classrooms today. Teachers are often focused on finishing the syllabus and may feel that engaging emotions and connecting with students is a waste of time.

4. Translation Method: The translation method is commonly used, especially in rural areas. While it helps students understand the content of a text, it hinders language learning itself. The primary goal of teaching the language is often overlooked, and more emphasis is placed on the content and themes of the text. As a result, the translation method becomes a significant obstacle in learning English effectively.

5. Mother Tongue Interference: Many language learning problems stem from the interference of the mother tongue when speaking English. Both teachers and students are usually more comfortable with their native language, which leads to the occasional mixing of English words into sentences in their mother tongue. They fail to recognize that each language has distinct stress, intonation, and pronunciation patterns, and this interference can disrupt proper language use [3]

The following solutions can be proposed to address the difficulties in teaching English:

Establishing a Positive Relationship with Students: It is crucial for educators to create a welcoming environment from the outset by greeting students with a friendly smile. Such gestures foster an immediate connection, facilitating a more positive and open learning atmosphere. When students feel personally engaged and comfortable with the teacher, they are more likely to find language learning less daunting and more accessible. A warm, approachable demeanor significantly enhances student interaction and participation.

Clarifying the Role of English: English provides numerous career opportunities across a wide range of fields, making it essential to define its place within the educational system. The policy regarding the role of English should be clearly outlined, considering its importance in areas such as science, technology, social sciences, philosophy, journalism, international trade, and diplomacy. This will help students recognize the value of learning English, not only as an academic subject but as a critical tool for success in the global arena.

Utilizing a Variety of Teaching Methods: Teachers should adopt diverse instructional strategies to effectively address the varied needs of their students. One such approach is incorporating language labs into lessons. Several pedagogical methods that can be employed in teaching English include:

1. Grammar Translation Method
2. Direct Method
3. Series Method
4. Variations of the Direct Method
5. Oral Approach/Situational Language Teaching
6. Audio-Lingual Method
7. Communicative Language Teaching
8. Directed Practice
9. Learning by Teaching

Selecting the appropriate teaching method for each particular topic enhances the overall effectiveness of language instruction, ensuring a comprehensive understanding and mastery of English by students.

Conclusion

In conclusion, addressing the challenges in teaching English requires a multifaceted approach. Building a positive rapport with students, clearly defining the role of English in education, and utilizing a variety of teaching methods can significantly enhance the learning experience. By fostering an environment of trust and engagement, students are more likely to develop confidence in their language skills. Additionally, adapting teaching strategies to suit different contexts and ensuring the use of modern resources, such as language labs, can further improve the effectiveness of instruction. Implementing these solutions can help overcome the obstacles in teaching English and make the learning process more efficient and enjoyable for students.

REFERENCES

1. Stone, G. Clarifying Communication Theories, Surjeet Publications, Delhi, 2003.
2. Wehmeyer, M.L. (2006). Universal Design for Learning, Access to the General Education Curriculum and Students with Mild Mental Disabilities. *Exceptionality*, 14(4), 225-235.
3. R. Sharma-“Problems and solutions of Teaching English”.

4. Xolnazarovich, B. X. (2024). Badiiy Matn Va uning Lingvopoetik Xususiyatlari. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 51, 298-303.
5. Berdiev, H. (2020). Лингвопоэтика Масалалари Тадқиқида “Девону Луғотит Турк” Нинг Ўрни. *Scienceproblems. uz*, 2(2), 7-7.
6. Xolnazarovich, B. X. (2024). “Devoni Hikmat” Asarining Tarixiy Leksikani O ‘Rganishdaga Ahamiyati Masalasiga Doir. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 51, 179-182.
7. Holnazarovich, B. H. (2020). Explanation of yurt building terms with through semantic methods. *International Journal of Engineering, Science and Mathematics*, 9(6), 9-13.
8. Бердиев, Х. Х. (2016). Метафорические термины в лексике юртовозведения. *Язык в сфере профессиональной коммуникации.*—Екатеринбург, 2016, 73-76.